

Rapid declines in waterbirds in urban wetlands - A case study from Perur Lake, Coimbatore (Supplementary)

This is supplementary information for the scientific paper published in Indian Birds#.

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⁽⁴⁾ Associated with “Perur Lake Forum,” a volunteer organization that is involved in community-based Citizen Science in Coimbatore (<https://perurlakeforum.org/>).

Introduction:

An annotated checklist of the birds recorded in Perur-Sundakamuthur Lake (Perur Lake henceforth), Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India, from May 2014 till April 2020 is provided below and is modelled on “The birds of the Delhi area: An annotated checklist” (Indian BIRDS Monograph 1 by Vyas, S 2019). Mr. Vyas mentions the importance of the enormous contribution made by various ornithologists and amateur bird enthusiasts for over a century leaving a rich history of records and observational notes that have made his monograph possible. While Coimbatore does not yet have such a storied history, our humble effort is a modest start in that direction.

This publication contains the following information about birds of Perur Lake:

1. Status of the species (Table 2 in main paper).
2. Population abundance (Table 3 in main paper and Table 1 here).
3. Bar charts detailing its presence in the lake.
4. Introductory boxes containing general observation of specific bird groups.
5. The variation in their numbers with high counts and water levels.
6. Notable behaviours including breeding when applicable.

Methodology:

We conducted a total of 67 counts in Perur Lake once a month in the period from May 2014 to April 2020, usually on second Saturdays. We walked along the fixed 2 km road during the morning for approximately two hours and counted all birds that were seen or heard and recorded the information in a checklist. This count can be characterized as a “total count” because visibility is nearly 100%.

Sample calculations of determining the distribution status of birds of Perur Lake are given below: (Refer Fig.2 and Table 3 of main paper)

Species	No. of sightings	Total count of birds	Overall Average (Total / 67)	Overall average of benchmark	RF No. of sightings / 67	PI Overall average/ benchmark average	Distribution Status [(RF+PI)/2] *100%	
							%	Status
Waterbirds								
Little Cormorant	57	2527	37.71	37.71	0.85	1.00	92.5%	Abundant
Indian Spot-billed Duck	63	2099	31.33		0.94	0.83	88.5%	Common
Painted Stork	45	795	11.86		0.67	0.31	49.0%	Fairly Common
Black-winged Stilt	23	174	2.59		0.34	0.07	20.5%	Uncommon
Striated Heron	8	11	0.16		0.12	0.004	6.2%	Rare
Non-Waterbirds								
House Crow	67	3405	50.82	50.82	1.00	1.00	100%	Abundant
Common Myna	67	2298	34.29		1.00	0.67	83.5%	Common
Yellow-billed Babbler	52	518	7.73		0.78	0.15	46.5%	Fairly Common
Red-vented Bulbul	30	76	1.13		0.45	0.02	23.5%	Uncommon
Paddyfield Pipit	12	21	0.31		0.18	0.006	9.3%	Rare

Table 1: Abundance of birds

Environmental Changes:

The three major environmental changes to Perur Lake are (1) Sand Mining, (2) Commercial Fishing and (3) Road Expansion whose details are given in the main paper.

Results:

The bird species recorded in Perur Lake during the study period are 125, belonging to 50 families and 19 orders. A bar chart is drawn for all birds that represents the presence or absence of the bird throughout the year, which is based on the survey data. We have given the line graphs for some birds depicting mean population trends with error bars. The error bar depicted is a “Standard Error (SE) of the Sample Mean” calculated using following formula:

$$\text{Standard Error of the Sample Mean} = \frac{\text{Standard Deviation}}{\sqrt{\text{Sample size}}}$$

The x-axis of these line graphs represents the calendar year from May to April and the y-axis represents the mean of the species with the error bars recorded in that period. For example, May 2015 to April 2016 is denoted as 2015-16 and similarly for the rest. In some special cases, composite graphs for select groups such as winter resident ducks and Egrets are also provided. The species accounts are based entirely on the results derived from our monthly counts.

There are 12 waterbirds whose names are given in red colour with asterisk (*) mark. These are the representative species that are discussed in Table 8 of the main paper.

Anseriformes: Anatidae

The bar charts for all the ducks sighted are given below:

<p>1. Lesser Whistling Duck</p>	<p>Lesser Whistling-Duck</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Sighting Count</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>January</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>February</td><td>4</td></tr> <tr><td>March</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>April</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>May</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>June</td><td>0</td></tr> <tr><td>July</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>August</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>September</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>October</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>November</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>December</td><td>2</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Sighting Count	January	3	February	4	March	3	April	0	May	1	June	0	July	2	August	2	September	2	October	2	November	2	December	2
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7. Indian Spot-billed Duck

1. Lesser Whistling Duck* (*Dendrocygna javanica*) has the distinction of being a Resident (R) and as well as a Local Migrant (LM). According to our records the population of this species increases in winter, specifically from January to March denoting its local migratory nature. While it is recorded throughout the year it is absent during the dry months of April to June, the single exception being May 2015 when five were seen due to the presence of water. Therefore, it has the dual status based on its nomadic habits in search of adequate water levels (Ali 2002). When the wetland experienced prolonged dryness due to the absence of monsoon rains from April 2016 to June 2018, this species was largely absent. The highest numbers recorded are 97 in January 2015, 159 in February 2016 and 74 in March 2016. The breeding season of this beautiful duck is from June to October (Rasmussen & Anderton 2012) and it has the potential to breed in Perur Lake if conditions are favourable.

Fig. 1: Mean population trend of the Lesser Whistling Duck with error bars

2. Cotton Pygmy Goose (*Nettapus coromandelianus*) is a Local Migrant (LM) duck in the area that was recorded only in four occurrences which are during the winter months from November 2014 to January 2015 and in December 2015. The highest counts were 17 and 18 in November and December of 2014 respectively. This species has not been sighted since December 2015.

Box 1:

The dabbling ducks of the genera *Spatula* & *Anas* favor shallow freshwater lakes (low to medium water levels) with extensive emergent vegetation (Madge & Burn 1988). The bar charts of these migrant ducks clearly capture the differences in their arrival in autumn and their departure in spring. The probable causes of its decline are discussed in the main paper. It is worth noting that from May 2014 to April 2015 an average of 223 winter migrant ducks were sighted. Currently, this figure stands at a dismal zero.

3. Garganey* (*Spatula querquedula*) is the most numerous of all the Winter Migrant (WM) ducks seen in Perur Lake. It is also the earliest to arrive such as in the month of August and the last to leave, which is by mid-April of the following year. It was recorded every month from December 2014 to April 2015, with peak numbers in February and March of 2015 of 532 and 436 respectively. Its sightings dwindled during the winter of 2015-16 to 21 and 152 in February and March of 2016. From September 2017 onwards the lake has undergone a severe habitat change like sand mining along with water impoundment for commercial fishing. Therefore, its numbers and that of other winter migrant ducks have dropped sharply. As a result, from April 2016 to November 2018, only a single bird was sighted in December 2016. Its latest sightings are from December 2018 to April 2019 and the highest count being 58 in March 2019.

Fig. 2: Mean population trend of the Garganey with error bars

4. Northern Shoveler (*Spatula clypeata*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) duck species that had consistent winter presence from December 2014 to March 2015. The counts in this period were 113, 140, 131, and 99 respectively. Due to inexplicable reasons, only three and nine individuals were sighted in October 2015 and February 2016 during the second season. Like Garganey, this species was largely absent since February 2016 until February 2019 except a single bird sighting in November 2017. The latest sightings for Shoveler were from February to April of 2019 and the counts were 40, 94 and 6 respectively at medium water level.

5. Northern Pintail (*Anas acuta*) is a long distant Winter Migrant (WM) duck species and according to our bar charts, it is usually the last to arrive and the earliest to leave, because its breeding grounds are in the northernmost location (Madge & Burn 1988). The population trend of this species shares the similar observation as that of the Garganey and the Northern Shoveler. The highest counts were in January and February 2015 when 218 and 436 were recorded respectively. It was largely unrecorded since February 2016 until January 2019 except the month of November 2017 when seven birds were observed. The latest sightings for Pintail were from January to March of 2019 out of which the highest count was 64, recorded in January 2019.

6. Common Teal (*Anas crecca*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species with an erratic presence in the lake. It has been recorded on five occasions and these few records indicate its nomadic nature, which is best designated as Uncertain (U). The highest count was 20 in February 2015 and the last two records were in November 2017 and February 2019 when the counts were 11 and three respectively.

Fig. 3: Composite graph of Winter Migrant Ducks

7. Indian Spot-billed Duck* (*Anas poecilorhyncha*) is primarily a Resident (R) species that has been consistently recorded since the inception of the survey in March 2014. In winter some additional birds add to the existing resident population increasing its numbers from February to May. This dabbling duck's highest counts were in September and October 2015 when 227 and 114 were seen and the water level was medium. However, in September and October 2014, when the lake was full the counts were 14 and 22 respectively. The breeding season is chiefly between July and September, but may extend to December in our area. In January 2015 a pair was observed in courtship behavior, which culminated in copulation. In October 2015 an adult bird was seen with a creche of five chicks and in December 2017 an adult pair was observed with four chicks (photograph in the inset), confirming its breeding status in the lake.

Fig. 4: Mean population trend of the Indian Spot-billed Duck with error bars

Galliformes: Phasianidae

9. Grey Francolin

8. Indian Peafowl (*Pavo cristatus*) is a Resident (R) species that was recorded frequently in our lake. The highest count was seven recorded in October 2016.

9. Grey Francolin (*Francolinus pondicerianus*) is also another Resident (R) species that has many records in our lake. The highest counts were five and four recorded in June 2015 and September 2019 respectively.

Podicipediformes: Podicipedidae

10. Little Grebe

10. Little Grebe* (*Tachybaptus ruficollis*) is a Resident (R) species that is recorded throughout the year and is extremely water dependent and rarely leaves it (Rasmussen & Anderton 2012). Accordingly, its highest counts were recorded when water levels are from full to medium; which was in September 2014, followed by January and February 2015, when 33, 50 and 29 birds were seen. After March 2016, this active diver was absent in the lake due to its dry condition, except for November 2017. The most recent observations were from May-November 2018 and in August 2019 and the highest number was 53 in July 2018. Even though the water level was full from August 2019 to March 2020, its numbers were depressed because of the disturbance caused by removal of vegetation for road construction in the lake bund. This is a potential breeder in this location when conditions are favourable and in September 2014 a flock with three chicks were spotted and thereby confirming its breeding status.

Fig. 5: Mean population trend of the Little Grebe with error bars

Columbiformes: Columbidae

11. Rock Pigeon (*Columba livia*) is a widespread Resident (R) species recorded year-round in our lake. The highest counts were an estimate of 50 and 60 recorded in November and December of 2015 respectively.

12. Eurasian Collared Dove (*Streptopelia decaocto*) is a Resident (R) species that was recorded year-round with occasional absences. Due to manmade disturbances in the lake, this species had a continuous span of absence from December 2016 to May 2018 except a single sighting in November 2017. The highest count was recorded in May 2019 when 12 individuals were sighted.

13. Spotted Dove (*Streptopelia chinensis*) is a Resident (R) species of our area and best described as Uncertain (U) due to infrequent sightings in our lake. The highest count of two birds has been recorded on a few occasions.

14. Laughing Dove (*Streptopelia senegalensis*) is a Resident (R) bird of our area that also has Uncertain (U) status. It has been sighted on two occasions in November 2015 and March 2020, when a single bird was recorded.

Cuculiformes: Cuculidae

17. Pied Cuckoo	<p>Jacobin Cuckoo</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
18. Asian Koel	<p>Asian Koel</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
19. Grey-bellied Cuckoo	<p>Gray-bellied Cuckoo</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
20. Common Hawk Cuckoo	<p>Common Hawk-Cuckoo</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

15. Greater Coucal (*Centropus sinensis*) is a Resident (R) species that is frequently recorded in our count. The highest counts ranging from three to four birds were recorded on multiple occasions.

16. Blue-faced Malkoha (*Phaenicophaeus viridirostris*) is a Resident (R) species that has a single sighting during the six-year count period when an individual was recorded in February 2020. Hence its status is Uncertain (U) in Perur Lake.

17. Pied Cuckoo (*Clamator jacobinus*) is a Resident (R)/Local Migrant (LM) species that was recorded six times in our entire count period from September 2014 to November 2016. Since then, this harbinger of the monsoon is unregistered in our lake. The highest count was five recorded in March 2016. This species also is classified as Uncertain (U).

18. Asian Koel (*Eudynamis scolopaceus*) is a Resident (R) species that was consistently recorded in Perur Lake. The highest count was four recorded on several occasions predominantly during the months between the middle of June to August coinciding with the

nesting of resident songbirds, on whom it is a brood parasite. This species is silent in winter, thus often overlooked and recorded as absent but becomes increasingly noisy with the advance of the hot weather (Ali 2002). Our field observations over the six-year period also verifies the fact that the incidence of this species is generally higher during the warmer months between April and August.

19. Grey-bellied Cuckoo (*Cacomantis passerinus*) is a Resident (R) of the general area but a rare visitor to urban locations. This was recorded only once in our count period in March 2018 and earning the designation as Uncertain (U).

20. Common Hawk Cuckoo (*Hierococcyx varius*) is a Resident (R) species that was recorded thrice in our count period also falling in the Uncertain (U) category. An individual was sighted in each occasion on July 2015, March 2016, and February 2019.

Caprimulgiformes: Apodidae

Box 2:

The Coimbatore district due to its location in the eastern slopes of the Western Ghats has several species of resident montane swifts and its lowlands are occasionally the beneficiary of their sightings, which are species #21, #22, #23 and #24 respectively whose accounts are given below. These sightings can be characterized as, "wanderers over a considerable radius from its roosting and nesting sites during the day's foraging, making erratic appearance in distant localities" (Ali & Ripley Vol IV 1968). In Perur Lake these species' erratic appearances, also called "irruptions" are seen as swift raiding parties that skims the surface of the lake for prey and take place mostly influenced by the local weather conditions and food availability. Therefore, these four swift species are classified as Uncertain (U).

<p>21. Brown-backed Needletail</p>	<p>Brown-backed Needletail</p> <table border="1"> <caption>Sighting Data for Brown-backed Needletail</caption> <thead> <tr> <th>Month</th> <th>Sighting Status</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>January</td><td>Present</td></tr> <tr><td>February</td><td>Absent</td></tr> <tr><td>March</td><td>Present</td></tr> <tr><td>April</td><td>Absent</td></tr> <tr><td>May</td><td>Absent</td></tr> <tr><td>June</td><td>Absent</td></tr> <tr><td>July</td><td>Present</td></tr> <tr><td>August</td><td>Absent</td></tr> <tr><td>September</td><td>Absent</td></tr> <tr><td>October</td><td>Absent</td></tr> <tr><td>November</td><td>Absent</td></tr> <tr><td>December</td><td>Absent</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Month	Sighting Status	January	Present	February	Absent	March	Present	April	Absent	May	Absent	June	Absent	July	Present	August	Absent	September	Absent	October	Absent	November	Absent	December	Absent
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21. Brown-backed Needletail (*Hirundapus giganteus*) is a Resident (R) species of the nearby Western Ghats, that was recorded five times in our count period. This species forages over forest canopy and it takes advantage of insect hatchings over waterways and lakes (Chantler & Boesman 2020), which explains its higher numbers from middle of June to August. The highest numbers were an estimate of 100 each recorded in August 2015 and July 2016.

22. Indian Swiftlet (*Aerodramus unicolor*) is a Resident (R) species but an uncommon visitor to Perur Lake. This species was recorded only twice during November 2018 and January 2019 when an estimate number of 50 and 10 were sighted.

23. Alpine Swift (*Tachymarptis melba*) is a Resident (R) species that was recorded twice in our count period when two individuals were sighted both in January of 2018 and 2019.

24. Indian House Swift (*Apus affinis*) is a Resident (R) species of the hillsides adjoining the Western Ghats and was sighted only once in our count period when an estimate of 25 were recorded in January 2019.

25. Asian Palm Swift (*Cypsiurus balasiensis*) is a Resident (R) species that is consistently recorded in our bird counts. This species is strongly associated with palm trees where it nests, which are present in our location. The few occasions when they were not registered are October 2016, September 2018, and April 2019. In plotting the monthly averages of this species, a noticeable dip was observed in the month of September indicating the possibility of post-breeding dispersal in a dynamic urban ecosystem. Also, we have registered a significant

decline in its overall population in this six-year period from an average of 93 in May 2015 – April 2016 to 22 in May 2018 – April 2019. The highest estimated number was 200 recorded on several occasions spanning from August 2014 till August 2015.

Fig. 6: Mean population trend of the Asian Palm Swift with error bars

Gruiformes: Rallidae

26. Common Moorhen	<p>Common Moorhen</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
27. Eurasian Coot	<p>Eurasian Coot</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
28. Grey-headed Swamphen	<p>Gray-headed Swamphen</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

29. White-breasted Waterhen

26. Common Moorhen (*Gallinula chloropus*) is a Resident (R) species that was predominantly sighted during the months from August to April and when the water level ranges from medium to full. It had a regular presence from August 2014 to May 2015 and intermittent records till April 2016. Since then, its population in the lake was drastically reduced. Its highest counts were 25 and 30 in January and April of 2015, respectively. After April 2016, the highest number was four in the month of December 2018. Its breeding season is from June to September or during the southwestern monsoon (Ali 2002).

27. Eurasian Coot* (*Fulica atra*) This Resident (R) species was once recorded in large numbers, but now is hardly seen in Perur Lake. It is mostly present when there is sufficient water, especially in high numbers, when its level is between medium and full. During the wetland years from 2014-16 it was recorded almost every month except for July 2014, June 2015, and April 2016. From August 2014 to February 2015, the range of variation was from 68 to 584, the highest counts occurring on the successive months of September and October 2014 as 575 and 584 respectively. It is possible that these numbers included both locally breeding birds and the local migrant population moving through the area. Due to lack of monsoon rains it was not seen at all from April 2016 to September 2017. It started reappearing at much reduced numbers and in an intermittent manner from October 2017 onwards and the last instance of its sighting being November 2019. The removal of vegetation and road expansion along the lake bund could be the probable reasons for their depressed numbers, despite favourable water levels. The highest count during this lean spell was 28 in September 2018. The Eurasian Coot is a breeder during the monsoonal months of July and August (Ali 2002) and in South India this breeding season can extend up to November (Rasmussen and Anderton 2012). A juvenile bird and a nest of grassy vegetation was seen in November 2014 and a single chick was sighted in March 2016, both confirming its breeding status in this location.

Fig. 7: Mean population trend of the Eurasian Coot with error bars

28. Grey-headed Swamphen (*Porphyrio poliocephalus*) is a Resident (R) species and recorded in large numbers until April 2016 when the water levels mostly vary from medium to full. Like Eurasian Coot (#27), the population level of this species also has significantly reduced probably due to the same reasons as stated above. This species had a continuous presence in the lake from August 2014 to August 2016 and since then it was recorded only at eight occasions in erratic manner. The highest counts recorded were 48 and 74 in February 2015 and March 2016 respectively, which is substantial when compared with the low range of counts recorded later, when they were 11 and 12 in November 2017 and June 2018. During the March 2016 count, when the highest number of this species was recorded, three chicks were sighted accompanying an adult indicating its possible breeding status.

29. White-breasted Waterhen (*Amaurornis phoenicurus*) is a Resident (R) species that was recorded year-round except during the drier months in the lake until May 2019. From June 2019 to Mar 2020, this bird was not recorded probably due to the disturbances from vegetation removal for the road expansion activity, carried out at the same period. The highest counts were six, five each in February 2015, December 2017, and February 2019 respectively. Its breeding season is from June to October (Ali 2002).

Charadriiformes: Recurvirostridae

Box 3:

Waders or Shorebirds as a rule of thumb prefer moist mudflats and shallow water levels in order to find prey and sustain themselves. These conditions are mostly available when water levels are between low and medium.

30. Black-winged Stilt

30. Black-winged Stilt* (*Himantopus himantopus*) is ideally classified as a Local Migrant (LM), but it is predominantly seen only in winter from January onwards. Its presence may be extended to July in this location, in order to breed if the situation is favourable. This long-legged shorebird is an ideal example to establish the necessary condition of medium water levels and exposed mudflats for their presence. Its sporadic absence may be due to search of such requirements. The highest counts of this bird were 26 and 56 in March 2015 and 2016 along with 22 in July 2018. This bird is versatile in its prey-finding techniques, because it can wade in deeper water, dabble like ducks and even swim if necessary (Ali 2002). Its breeding season is from April to August, and in July 2019 an individual chick was spotted (photographic inset in Fig.8) along with an adult pair confirming its breeding status in the lake.

Fig. 8: Mean population trend of the Black-winged Stilt with error bars

Charadriiformes: Charadriidae

<p>31. Red-wattled Lapwing</p>	<p>Red-wattled Lapwing</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
<p>32. Kentish Plover</p>	<p>Kentish Plover</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
<p>33. Little Ringed Plover</p>	<p>Little Ringed Plover</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

31. Red-wattled Lapwing (*Vanellus indicus*) is a Resident (R) species that was recorded throughout the year in our lake. However, from September 2016 till May 2017 we recorded this reliable sentinel only twice. This was probably because of extremely dry conditions due to the failure of both monsoons. The highest counts were 15, 16 and 24 recorded in September, October of 2015, and June 2018 respectively. Its breeding season is chiefly from March to August (Ali 2002) and a juvenile was observed in July 2015.

Fig. 9: Mean population trend of the Red-wattled Lapwing with error bars

32. Kentish Plover (*Charadrius alexandrinus*) is a species that was recorded only twice during our count period, which were in October and November of 2017 when 12 and two birds were sighted respectively. Its status is Uncertain (U).

33. Little Ringed Plover* (*Charadrius dubius*) has two distinct populations; the larger group being the winter migrant *C.d.curonicus* and the possible residential breeder *C.d.jerdoni* (Hayman et al 1986) present in much smaller numbers. An overwhelming number of the birds sighted during the months from September to April are most likely the migrant population. This species was recorded in February and March of 2015 and 2016 and in May, June, September, and October of 2015. It was absent from August to November 2018, and from June 2019 to April 2020, except for three birds seen in February 2020. The highest counts were recorded in March 2015 and 2016 as 84 and 39, and in October and December 2017 as 23 and 26. In May 2015 three individuals were seen and in June 2015 a single bird was spotted. However, the fast-changing water level due to monsoon rains prevented its possible nesting from being confirmed.

Fig. 10: Mean population trend of the Little Ringed Plover with error bars

Charadriiformes: Jacanidae

34. Pheasant-tailed Jacana (*Hydrophasianus chirurgus*) is a species with Uncertain (U) status that has been recorded only during four instances. This species has not been recorded since January 2015. The counts during these sightings were one each, two and 17 in September, October, December of 2014, and January 2015 respectively.

35. Bronze-winged Jacana (*Metopidius indicus*) is also a species with Uncertain (U) status that was recorded only twice. A single individual was sighted on January and August of 2015.

Charadriiformes: Scolopacidae

<p>36. Temminck's Stint</p>	<p>Temminck's Stint</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
<p>37. Little Stint</p>	<p>Little Stint</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
<p>38. Common Sandpiper</p>	<p>Common Sandpiper</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
<p>39. Green Sandpiper</p>	<p>Green Sandpiper</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
<p>40. Common Greenshank</p>	<p>Common Greenshank</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
<p>41. Marsh Sandpiper</p>	<p>Marsh Sandpiper</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

42. Wood Sandpiper

36. Temminck's Stint (*Calidris temminckii*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species that has a regular presence in the lake but was unrecorded during the winter months of the years 2015-16 and 2019-20. The highest count of this species was 18 in December 2017 when the water level was low and its next highest count was eight in four other occasions when the water level was low to medium.

37. Little Stint (*Calidris minuta*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species that has been recorded in all winters except that of 2019-20. The highest counts of this species were 49 in March 2015, 32 and 22 recorded in January and February of 2017, also the 22 and 21 in February and March of 2019.

38. Common Sandpiper* (*Actitis hypoleucos*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) shorebird that is consistently seen from August to April of the wetland year. It arrives as early as August and is the last to leave, which is in April just like the dabbling duck Garganey. The highest counts of this species are 21 in March 2015, followed by 35 and 23 in October and November 2017. The water impoundment for commercial fishing has reduced its numbers from 2018 onwards.

Fig. 11: Mean population trend of the Common Sandpiper with error bars

39. Green Sandpiper (*Tringa ochropus*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species that has been recorded from October to April. This atypical sandpiper which is less gregarious than its cousins, keeps either singly or in twos and threes and seldom seen in voluntary association with other species. During the first two wetland years, it was mostly sighted between the months of January and March, when the highest count was six in March 2016. Thereafter its sightings were far fewer and the highest count was 15 recorded in November 2016.

40. Common Greenshank (*Tringa nebularia*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species that has been recorded mostly from October to April. This species was recorded mostly during the months from February to April during the first two years, when the highest count was 14 in April 2015. Since then, its notable high counts were 14 and 16 recorded in December 2017 and April 2019 respectively.

41. Marsh Sandpiper (*Tringa stagnatilis*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species that has sparse records in our lake and is rare when compared with the rest of the *Tringa* cousins. During the time span from May 2014 to April 2016, there were only three sightings of three birds each in February and March of 2015 and March 2016. Then in the succeeding four-year period the sightings were in January and November 2017, and in February 2019 when three, five and seven birds were recorded respectively. This species may be classified as a Passage Migrant (PM) with the caveat that there are very few records in Perur Lake.

42. Wood Sandpiper* (*Tringa glareola*) is the most numerous Winter Migrant (WM) shorebird species seen in Perur Lake. This typical representative of the Scolopacidae group exhibits gregariousness more than other sandpipers. It starts to arrive in September and its numbers gradually increase till October and then decrease by January. With the start of the northward migration its numbers increase noticeably in February, peaking in March and tapering by the end of April. Its highest counts were 62 and 100 in March 2015 and 2016, but in February 2017 it was a mere 17. Its sightings have drastically reduced due to the water impoundment in the lake for commercial fishing.

Fig. 12: Mean population trend of the Wood Sandpiper with error bars

Charadriiformes: Laridae

43. Whiskered Tern (*Chlidonias hybrida*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species which is recorded sporadically as noted in our previous publication (G. Parameswaran & R. Sivashankar 2018). However, this species was recorded at least once in every season with the minimum count of one each in November 2016 and October 2017. The highest counts were 58 and 50 in April 2019 and January 2020 respectively and thereby indicating its nomadic behavior in search of lakes where prey is abundant and water levels are full.

44. River Tern (*Sterna aurantia*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species whose occurrence is rare in Perur Lake and exhibits a nomadic behavior. It has been sighted only at four occasions in November 2014, January 2016, October 2018, and March 2020 when one, two, one and three birds were recorded respectively.

Ciconiiformes: Ciconiidae

45. Asian Openbill	<p>Asian Openbill</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
46. Woolly-necked Stork	<p>Woolly-necked Stork</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
47. Painted Stork	<p>Painted Stork</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

45. Asian Openbill* (*Anastomus oscitans*) This Local Migrant (LM) species is consistently seen in Perur Lake throughout the year. Its higher numbers span the timeframe from October to June of the succeeding year, and reduced numbers from July to September, possibly due to the outward migration of breeding birds. When the water level is either low or medium with good mudflat exposure, its highest counts are often registered; while high water level signifies the opposite. The high counts of this species are from October, November, December of 2016, and March of 2017 which are 126, 116, 133 and 133 respectively. From June 2017 to April 2020 this species was scarcely seen and the notable exception being in November 2018, when 18 individuals were seen in flight. The principal reason for such a lean count could be the water was maintained at high levels to facilitate commercial fishing.

Fig. 13: Mean population trend of the Asian Openbill with error bars

46. Woolly-necked Stork (*Ciconia episcopus*) is a species in our area that was sighted only at five occasions in winter months earning the status of Uncertain (U). The highest count was three recorded on March 2015 and April 2019. In addition, Sharang (2016) also reported a flock of 62 birds of this stork species on 29 March 2016 from this lake. These observations, even though scanty in nature, probably indicate that this species might be using Perur Lake as a transit point during spring migration only. A small population of Woolly-necked Stork breeds in the neighboring districts of Kerala (Sashikumar et al. 2011).

47. Painted Stork (*Mycteria leucocephala*) is a Local Migrant (LM) species whose counts are higher when the water levels vary from low to medium, a conducive condition for prey-finding. The presence of this species is sharply reduced when the water level is full. Its highest counts were in the low water level months of June and July 2019 when 77 and 180 individuals recorded respectively. However, this species was absent from February to June of 2018 despite the low water level condition. The probable reason for this could be the disturbance due to sand mining that happened in the second half of 2017. This species breeds in southern India between August and January, varying with local conditions (Ali 2002; Rasmussen & Anderton 2012). It is listed as Near Threatened due to its moderate population reduction owing to hunting, drainage, and pollution (Rahmani 2012).

Suliformes: Anhingidae and Phalacrocoracidae

Box 4:

The birds in this group which are mostly represented by the Oriental Darter (*Anhinga melanogaster*), the Little Cormorant (*Microcarbo niger*) and the Indian Cormorant (*Phalacrocorax fuscicollis*) have increased in numbers during this study period, starting from August 2018. However, these higher numbers are deceptive indicators of ecosystem's health because they are seldom seen feeding in the lake. Also, there is a high probability based on their behavior, that these group of birds are either roosting or nesting in the trees located at the far end of the lake by using the water as a predatory barrier (Subramanya 2005 and C Shashikumar et al. 2014). Only by continuous monitoring can one make the determination, whether this increase can be sustained in future.

48. Oriental Darter	<p>Oriental Darter</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
49. Little Cormorant	<p>Little Cormorant</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
50. Indian Cormorant	<p>Indian Cormorant</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
51. Great Cormorant	<p>Great Cormorant</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

48. Oriental Darter (*Anhinga melanogaster*) This Resident (R) bird is recorded year-round with some occasional absence. From 2014-16 it was not sighted in May and September of

2014, and in March and April of 2016, due to lack of adequate levels of water. The high counts in this period were 22, 24 and 23 in November and December of 2014 and September 2015. This was followed by very few sightings from May 2016 to May 2018, due to the failure of monsoon rains and the extended dry spell. Once the lake bed was deepened in 2017 by sand mining and the subsequent water storage to aid commercial fishing, the population of this species exploded and the high counts were 70, 165, 65 during October and November of 2018 and January 2019. The nesting and breeding of this species were recorded in October and November of 2019. This species is listed as Near Threatened by IUCN 3.1 because of its moderate population reduction due to pollution, drainage, hunting, and collection of eggs and nestlings (Rahmani 2012).

Fig. 14: Mean population trend of the Oriental Darter with error bars

49. Little Cormorant (*Microcarbo niger*) This Resident (R) cormorant species has the unique distinction of being the waterbird benchmark, and has the highest average count over the six-year period from May 2014 to April 2020. These numbers are usually recorded during high water levels, but unlike the darter and other cormorant species it can still be seen when there is hardly any water. This species was absent from May-July of 2014, then from March-June of 2015 and during a long spell from May 2016 to July 2018. The reason for these absences is the dry spells that the wetland experienced either due to the seasonal conditions or the lack of monsoon rain. Once commercial fishing was established from October 2018 onwards its population also exploded like the Oriental Darter (#48) and the high counts were 187 and 189 in November and December of 2018. This species is a potential breeder when conditions are favourable.

Fig. 15: Mean population trend of the Little Cormorant with error bars

50. Indian Cormorant (*Phalacrocorax fuscicollis*) is a Resident (R) species which had sparse presence in this lake, started to appear in higher numbers from August 2018 onwards and was frequently recorded. This increase in its numbers was probably due to the presence of the predatory water barrier established for commercial fishing and its absence during the drier months of May and June are thus explained. The highest counts were 97 and 92 in September and December of 2018 respectively. This species probably breeds in the area in other water bodies.

51. Great Cormorant (*Phalacrocorax carbo*) is a Local Migrant (LM) species that is a wanderer in search of water and its sighting is based on this feature in our lake. Its recent observations were in October, November of 2017, August 2018, November 2019, and February 2020. The highest count was five recorded in February 2020 when the water level was full.

Pelecaniformes: Pelecanidae

52. Spot-billed Pelican (*Pelecanus philippensis*) is a Local Migrant (LM) species, but an opportunistic breeder in suitable localities from October to April. This species is an irregular visitor to our lake and was recorded only at five occurrences before November 2016 with a

highest of 25 in September 2015. In January 2017, despite low water level, a record 170 individuals of this species were recorded probably due to lack of water in surrounding wetlands. In April 2019, 95 birds were registered at medium water level. This species has bred in Vellalore Lake, which is in southeast Coimbatore from November 2018 to April 2019 and November 2019 to March 2020, because the water level and other conditions were favorable in that location (G. Parameswaran, *in litt*, e-mail dated 28 January 2019). The increased measures of protection enabled a recovery in numbers of this species and it was down listed from Vulnerable to Near Threatened in 2007 as per IUCN 3.1 and (Rahmani 2012).

Pelecaniformes: Ardeidae

<p>53. Yellow Bittern</p>	<p>Yellow Bittern</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
<p>54. Cinnamon Bittern</p>	<p>Cinnamon Bittern</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
<p>55. Grey Heron</p>	<p>Grey Heron</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
<p>56. Purple Heron</p>	<p>Purple Heron</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

53. Yellow Bittern (*Ixobrychus sinensis*) and 54. Cinnamon Bittern (*Ixobrychus cinnamomeus*) are the two species of charismatic skulkers that was recorded infrequently between February 2015 and April 2016. Since then both the bittern species were unrecorded in our counts and their status is Uncertain (U). Yellow Bittern was recorded in February, March & April 2015 and March 2016 and their numbers were three,

two, two, and one, respectively. Cinnamon Bittern was recorded in February 2015 and April 2016; in both occurrences, a single bird was sighted.

55. Grey Heron (*Ardea cinerea*) This large and gangly Resident (R) heron is consistently seen in the wetland flying with folded wings and a bowed wingbeat. This species is present in higher numbers when water level is between low and medium. Its notable absence was in April 2017 and in November 2017, because of dryness and the after effects of sand mining operation respectively. The notable high counts are 46 and 21 in September and October of 2015 and 22 and 32 in April and June of 2019. The reason for its increased presence since 2017 needs to be carefully monitored.

Fig. 16: Mean population trend of the Grey Heron with error bars

56. Purple Heron (*Ardea purpurea*) is a Resident (R) species that was observed consistently from June 2014 to August 2016, except in May 2014 and July 2015. The highest counts during this time frame were 11 birds each in April 2015 and February 2016. From September 2016 onwards its sightings have been reduced and the highest count was five recorded in October 2018. This species is largely crepuscular, perhaps shy, and secretive, keeping to dense reed cover where it may be easily overlooked. Its breeding season in India ranges from June to March depending on locality (Ali 2002), and in neighboring Kerala, it reportedly breeds in July and August (C Sashikumar et al. 2011).

Box 5:

The three Egrets namely the Great Egret (*Ardea alba*), the Intermediate Egret (*Ardea intermedia*) and the Little Egret (*Egretta garzetta*) as a group are Local Migrants (LM) in our area, whose population varies according to water conditions (Ali & Ripley Vol – I, 1968). These species are present in higher numbers when the water levels are between low and medium. They move out of the area for breeding (Sashikumar et al. 2011), which is from May to November. The higher numbers observed in Perur Lake between March and May are probably the local migratory movement to their breeding locations in the nearby districts of Kerala like Palakkad (Subramanya 2005, Sashikumar et al. 2014).

57. Great Egret	<p>Great Egret</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
58. Intermediate Egret	<p>Intermediate Egret</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
59. Little Egret	<p>Little Egret</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
60. Cattle Egret	<p>Cattle Egret</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

57. Great Egret (*Ardea alba*) is a Local Migrant (LM) species that has been recorded year-round in Perur Lake from May 2014 to April 2016. During this period its absences were in August to October 2014, July 2015, and December 2015. Its counts usually ranged between one and eight, with a notable exception being in April 2016, when it was an astounding 31

individuals possibly migrating through the area. It was recorded in low numbers from June 2016 till July 2018, which included many months when they were absent. The highest counts were ten and 11 in January and June of 2019.

58. Intermediate Egret (*Ardea intermedia*) This medium sized white egret is a Local Migrant (LM) species which has been mostly sighted when water levels are between Medium and Low. During the two-year time span between May 2014 to April 2016, this bird was absent from May to June of 2014, when the wetland was dry, and from September to November 2014, when the water level was Full. The highest counts were 24 in April 2016 and 17 in December 2015. From July 2016 to April 2019 its sightings were reduced and the pattern was intermittent, and the highest count was five in July 2019.

59. Little Egret* (*Egretta garzetta*) This is a Local Migrant (LM) species which is recorded consistently throughout the year in the wetland. Its highest numbers are usually recorded when the water level varies from medium to low, which is also the preference of Intermediate and Great Egrets. During the period from May 2014 to April 2016 the highest counts of this species were 60, 116, and 215 in March 2015, April 2015 and April 2016 indicating its local migration through the area. Due to sand mining and water impoundment for commercial fishing its overall population has reduced since May 2017. However, the species was recorded throughout the year except in December 2017, May 2018, and November 2019. The highest count during this time frame was in May 2019 when 34 birds were sighted.

Fig. 17: Mean population trend of the Little Egret with error bars

Fig. 18: Composite graph of average population trend of Great, Intermediate and Little Egret

60. Cattle Egret (*Bubulcus ibis*) This species is principally a Local Migrant (LM) in our area, but is recorded throughout the year. The key requirement for this species seems to be moist areas surrounding the wetlands. From May 2014 to April 2016 the highest counts of this bird were in November 2014 and April 2015, which were 37 and 40. Its populations dropped during the dry years starting from latter half of 2016, including the entire year of 2017 and up until the first half of 2018. In our previous publication (G. Parameswaran & R. Sivashankar 2018) we wrote that “birds with breeding plumage were observed during its breeding months of November to March; however, no nests were recorded in the vicinity of the lake”. The highest counts were 21 and 20 recorded in February 2020 and August 2018, respectively. The occasional nesting of Cattle Egrets in Greater Coimbatore area was in Singanallur lake reported by (Rajah Jayapal, in litt, e-mail dated 14 September 2021) who has stated that, “I have seen a couple of active nests along Singanallur bund vegetation on 26th of January 2018 located in a *Prosopis* tree. It was well hidden unlike other waterbird nests and therefore there might be more in the vicinity.”

Fig. 19: Mean population trend of the Cattle Egret with error bars

61. Indian Pond Heron* (*Ardeola grayii*) This species is a widespread Resident (R) that is recorded throughout the year. Its pattern of occurrence is like that of the Cattle Egret with some minor differences as to its status. The water level preference is from medium to low, which is similar to ducks, shorebirds, and egrets. From May 2014 to April 2016 the highest counts were 65 and 64 in January 2015 and April 2016. The population of this species has

significantly dropped since May 2016 and the plausible reasons could be disturbances due to sand mining of the wetland, the removal of vegetation for road building and commercial fishing. The highest counts recorded during the study period were 58, 31 and 40 in May 2016 and 2019, and in March 2020.

Fig. 20: Mean population trend with error bars of the Indian Pond Heron

62. Striated Heron (*Butorides striata*) is a species with Uncertain (U) designation in Perur Lake. In the first two years of the count, this species was recorded at five instances with the highest count of four in April 2016 and it was recorded only twice in the last four years. These low records are possibly due to its shy and retiring nature along with its crepuscular behavior.

63. Black-crowned Night Heron (*Nycticorax nycticorax*) is a Resident (R) species with sparse sightings in our lake, which is also crepuscular and nocturnal except in breeding season. It was largely absent from May 2016 till August 2018 except when a single bird was sighted in April 2017. The highest count from May 2014 to April 2016 was in February 2016 when 18 individuals of this species were sighted flying overhead. Most of them were immature or juvenile birds, indicating its possible breeding in the area. The recent highest count was 16 recorded in March 2020.

Pelecaniformes: Threskiornithidae

64. Glossy Ibis

65. Black-headed Ibis	<p>Black-headed Ibis</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
66. Eurasian Spoonbill	<p>Eurasian Spoonbill</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

64. Glossy Ibis (*Plegadis falcinellus*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) in our area that was recorded mostly during September to March except on a single occasion in July 2018 when 3 birds were sighted. The highest counts of this species were 53 and 68 recorded in September and October of 2015 respectively at medium water levels. This can probably explain its long absence from April 2016 until June 2018 due to the continuous low water levels in the lake along with the disturbances due to Sand Mining. Since 2018, the species was recorded on five occasions with the maximum of 27 in January 2019.

65. Black-headed Ibis (*Threskiornis melanocephalus*) is a Local Migrant (LM) species that was recorded erratically and in lower numbers. Its highest counts were six in Nov 2018 and four in April 2017 and Sep 2019 respectively. It is worth noting that most of these sightings starting from July 2018 to September 2019 are registered as fly-overs possibly due to the environmental disturbances in the lake. According to Rahmani (2012), this species is nomadic and migratory in nature depending upon the availability of water and it is listed as 'Near Threatened' by IUCN 3.1.

66. Eurasian Spoonbill (*Platalea leucorodia*) is a Local Migrant (LM) species which is also nomadic and erratic in its occurrence. Its preference is for standing water with shallow depth where it is often seen feeding in the company of Painted Storks and Little Egrets. This species was recorded only once in the two-year period from May 2014 to April 2016. The highest counts were 32 in April 2019 when the water level was at medium and 25 in June 2019 at low water level. This species has also nested in Vellalore lake located in southeast Greater Coimbatore from November 2018 to March 2019 according to (G. Parameswaran, *in litt*, e-mail dated 26 September 2021).

Accipitriformes: Accipitridae

67. Oriental Honey Buzzard	<p>Oriental Honey-buzzard</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>	
68. Black Eagle	<p>Black Eagle</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>	
69. Booted Eagle	<p>Booted Eagle</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>	
70. Western Marsh Harrier	<p>Eurasian Marsh-Harrier</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>	
71. Shikra	<p>Shikra</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>	
72. Black Kite	<p>Black Kite</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>	

73. Brahminy Kite

67. Oriental Honey Buzzard (*Pernis ptilorhynchus*) is a Resident (R) species that has been sighted in our lake with intermittent frequency. This species has both Resident and Winter Migrant populations spread throughout the subcontinent, subject to considerable movements related to food supply. They inhabit well-wooded country and groves in semi-urban areas. The highest count was two recorded in February 2017 and January 2018.

68. Black Eagle (*Ictinaetus malaiensis*) is a resident species of our forest and adjoining areas and was sighted only once in February 2017. Its status is classified as Uncertain (U).

69. Booted Eagle (*Hieraaetus pennatus*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species that has been recorded only thrice, a single bird on each occasion. Since the autumn of 2016, this species has been unrecorded in our lake and currently its status is Uncertain (U).

70. Western Marsh Harrier (*Circus aeruginosus*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) raptor species that has been recorded six times during the first two years of our bird count. This species has been unrecorded in Perur Lake since March 2016. The absence of its sightings is probably due to the various disturbances in the wetland. The status of this species is Uncertain (U).

71. Shikra (*Accipiter badius*) is a Resident (R) species that has been recorded frequently and in a random fashion. The highest count was three birds sighted in March 2016.

Box 6:

Black Kite (*Milvus migrans*) and Brahminy Kite (*Haliastur indus*) are our two common Resident (R) raptors that are frequently sighted in this lake. They exhibit a complementary relationship where the Black Kite's numbers are generally higher during the months from April to August when there is less water in the wetland and correspondingly the Brahminy Kite's numbers are higher during the rest of the year when there is more water, which is reflected in our data (Fig. 21).

72. Black Kite (*Milvus migrans*) is a Resident (R) species that was regularly recorded in our lake. This species is one of the world's most adaptable raptor, and congregates in large numbers around cities, towns, villages and in the vicinity of nomadic settlements and prone to local migration from rainfall areas (Naoroji 2006). The highest counts were 52 and 17 recorded in May 2015 and August 2016 respectively.

73. Brahminy Kite (*Haliastur indus*) is a Resident (R) species that was almost always recorded in the lake with very few exceptions, and always present when there is water. Its population is prone to cyclical movements towards well-watered locations subject to monsoon conditions (Naoroji 2006). The highest counts were ten and eight recorded in October 2016 and September 2018.

Fig. 21: Monthly average comparison of Black Kite and Brahminy Kite

Strigiformes: Strigidae

74. Spotted Owlet (*Athene brama*) is a Resident (R) species that has sparse sightings in Perur Lake. We recorded this species only five times in the count period and the highest count was in October 2015 when two individuals were recorded. The removal of its roosting trees for road construction has possibly pushed this species to the status of Uncertain (U).

Bucerotiformes: Upupidae

75. Common Hoopoe (*Upupa epops*) is a Resident (R) species that was recorded only four times in the count period and therefore Uncertain (U). Single bird was sighted in each occasion of August 2014, May 2015, June 2016, and July 2019.

Bucerotiformes: Bucerotidae

76. Indian Grey Hornbill (*Ocyrceros birostris*) is a species that is uncommon in our general area and rare in Perur Lake. This species was recorded only once in our count period when an individual was sighted in October 2014 and thus Uncertain (U).

Coraciiformes: Alcedinidae

77. Common Kingfisher (*Alcedo atthis*) is a Resident (R) species that is recorded consistently when there is water in the lake. It is either seen as a single bird or in pairs when it dashes off at top speed, low over the water. However, from November 2016 till November 2018 this common bird was unrecorded because of the absence of water and probably due to the disturbances to the wetland from June 2017 till September 2017. The highest counts were recorded during April 2015 and November 2019 when five and three birds were sighted respectively.

78. Stork-billed Kingfisher (*Pelargopsis capensis*) is a species that is Uncertain (U) in our area and rare in Perur Lake. A single bird was sighted in February 2019.

79. White-throated Kingfisher (*Halcyon smyrnensis*) is a Resident (R) species which is also our most common kingfisher, that has been recorded throughout the year. It has been consistently registered even during spells of low water levels and occasional dryness, which existed from May 2016 till June 2018, thus confirming its least dependence on the presence of water. The highest counts of this species were in January 2015 and January 2016 when 15 and ten birds were sighted.

Fig. 22: Mean population trend with error bars of the White-throated Kingfisher

80. Pied Kingfisher (*Ceryle rudis*) is a Resident (R) and water dependent species that is recorded sparsely in our lake. It was intermittently recorded when the water levels were medium or high during the period from August 2014 till March 2016. This species was last recorded in July 2016 and its highest count was in December 2015 when four individuals were sighted.

Coraciiformes: Meropidae

81. Green Bee-eater (*Merops orientalis*) is a species that is fairly common and widespread in our area, but was sighted only twice in Perur Lake during the time period. In the months of May 2015 and May 2017, five birds and a single individual were recorded, respectively. Its status qualifies as Uncertain (U).

82. Blue-tailed Bee-eater (*Merops philippinus*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species that was predominantly recorded from September to March in our lake. This species when compared with the more widespread resident Green Bee-eater (#81) prefers urban groves, wetlands, and streams. The highest counts were an estimate of 100 and 150 registered in October and November of 2014. It has significantly declined during our survey period in general, with a pronounced dip in its average population from 2014-2015, possibly due to the occasional dryness and continuous disturbances in the lake like road building.

Fig. 23: Mean population trend with error bars of the Blue-tailed Bee-eater

Coraciiformes: Coraciidae

83. Indian Roller

83. Indian Roller (*Coracias benghalensis*) is a Resident (R) species that has been frequently sighted in our lake. However, a continuous absence was observed from August 2018 till April 2020 except in July 2019. The highest number was four recorded in November 2015, July, and September of 2016.

Piciformes: Megalaimidae

84. Coppersmith Barbet

84. Coppersmith Barbet (*Psilopogon haemacephalus*) is a Resident (R) species that was recorded sparsely in our counts. The highest count was six in May 2017.

Piciformes: Picidae

85. Black-rumped Flameback

85. Black-rumped Flameback (*Dinopium benghalense*) is a Resident (R) species that is frequently recorded with occasional gaps. The highest count was in November 2018 when four individuals were recorded.

Falconiformes: Falconidae

86. Peregrine Falcon (*Falco peregrinus*) has two subspecies that can be seen in our area. Both are rare in our general area and in Perur Lake.

A) Shaheen Falcon (*Falco peregrinus peregrinator*) is a Resident (R) species of our area, that was recorded twice in our count when a single individual was sighted in March 2016 and April 2018.

B) Peregrine Falcon (*Falco peregrinus calidus*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species that was sighted only once in October 2014.

Since there are only a few sightings it falls within the status of Uncertain (U).

Psittaciformes: Psittaculidae

87. Rose-ringed Parakeet (*Psittacula krameri*) is a common and widespread Resident (R) Parakeet species of our area that was recorded year-round in Perur Lake. Their average counts were noticeably higher during the months from October to March. The highest counts were 61 and 47 recorded in October 2014 and October 2016.

Passeriformes: Oriolidae

88. Eurasian Golden Oriole (*Oriolus oriolus*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) passerine that is sporadically recorded in our lake. The highest count was three recorded in December 2019 and February 2020.

Passeriformes: Artamidae

89. Ashy Woodswallow (*Artamus fuscus*) is a species of our area that is infrequently recorded in our lake and the highest count was five each in August and September of 2018. This qualifies as Uncertain (U).

Passeriformes: Aegithinidae

90. Common Iora (*Aegithina tiphia*) is a songbird of our area and has been recorded only once when an individual was sighted in February 2020 and thus Uncertain (U).

Passeriformes: Dicruridae

91. Black Drongo (*Dicrurus macrocercus*) is a Resident (R) songbird that was sighted frequently in our lake, and its highest count was nine in April 2016.

Passeriformes: Monarchidae

92. Indian Paradise-flycatcher (*Terpsiphone paradisi*) is a songbird of our area that falls under the Uncertain (U) category, because this gorgeous bird has been recorded only once in November 2018.

Passeriformes: Laniidae

93. Brown Shrike (*Lanius cristatus*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) songbird which is recorded in small numbers with some regularity. The sightings of this species have probably decreased due to removal of vegetation and road construction. The highest count was four registered in March 2017.

Passeriformes: Corvidae

96. Large-billed Crow

94. Rufous Treepie (*Dendrocitta vagabunda*) is a Resident (R) songbird of our area with multiple observations and the highest being 11 in May 2017.

95. House Crow (*Corvus splendens*) is a Resident (R) species that is also the most abundant songbird recorded in our lake. Their numbers are usually estimates during the count period because of its widespread occurrence. The two largest counts were 126 and 110 in April 2015 and October 2016, respectively.

Fig. 24: Mean population trend with error bars of the House Crow

96. Large-billed Crow (*Corvus macrorhynchos*) is a Resident (R) songbird that is common in our lake usually seen mixed with House Crow but in lower numbers. The highest counts were 25 each in December 2014 and November 2015.

Passeriformes: Cisticolidae

97. Common Tailorbird (*Orthotomus sutorius*) is a Resident (R) songbird that is consistently recorded in our count. The highest counts were five each observed in January 2015 and in January 2019.

Fig. 25: Mean population trend with error bars of the Common Tailorbird

98. Ashy Prinia (*Prinia socialis*) is a Resident (R) species that has been recorded in all our count sessions. The highest count was 25 in November 2014 and currently its numbers have reduced sharply, whose probable reasons are removal of vegetation and road building activities.

Fig. 26: Mean population trend with error bars of the Ashy Prinia

Passeriformes: Acrocephalidae

99. Booted Warbler	<p>Booted Warbler</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
100. Sykes's Warbler	<p>Sykes's Warbler</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
101. Blyth's Reed Warbler	<p>Blyth's Reed Warbler</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

102. Clamorous Reed Warbler

99. Booted Warbler (*Iduna caligata*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) Warbler species that has been recorded regularly in our lake. This species is usually seen singly or in small flocks, foraging among leaves and flowers in the trees that are present on the shores. The highest count was six recorded in March 2017.

100. Sykes's Warbler (*Iduna rama*) is a species that has been sighted only twice in our count period. A single individual was recorded in February 2017 and January 2019 and is of Uncertain (U) status.

101. Blyth's Reed Warbler (*Acrocephalus dumetorum*) is the most numerous Winter Migrant (WM) Warbler species of our area that has been observed consistently during the counts from November to April. The highest count was 18 recorded in November 2016. The population of this species has declined significantly, and the probable reasons are the same as that of Ashy Prinia (#98).

Fig. 27: Mean population trend with error bars of the Blyth's Reed Warbler

102. Clamorous Reed Warbler (*Acrocephalus stentoreus*) is a Local Migrant (LM) Warbler species that has been recorded only thrice in our count. A single individual was recorded in

November 2015, while two and three birds were seen in January and February of 2017, respectively.

Passeriformes: Hirundinidae

<p>103. Barn Swallow</p>	<p>Barn Swallow</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
<p>104. Red-rumped Swallow</p>	<p>Red-rumped Swallow</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
<p>105. Northern House Martin</p>	<p>Common House-Martin</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

103. Barn Swallow (*Hirundo rustica*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species that has been recorded consistently in our wetland from October to March. This gregarious species had an estimated high count of 420 in February 2016, but has significantly declined in numbers in the recent counts.

104. Red-rumped Swallow (*Cecropis daurica*) is a species of our area that has been predominantly recorded between the months of October and March, exhibiting its Local Migratory characteristics (LM). The highest count of this gregarious species which breeds elsewhere in our area, was estimated to be 150 each in February 2016 and January 2020.

105. Northern House Martin (*Delichon urbicum*) is a passage migrant species of our area during February and March that has been recorded only once during the count of February 2016 when a single individual was sighted. It falls in the Uncertain (U) category.

Passeriformes: Pycnonotidae

106. Red-vented Bulbul (*Pycnonotus cafer*) is a Resident (R) species that has been recorded consistently in Perur Lake. The highest counts were 12 and 13 in October 2014 and January 2020.

Passeriformes: Sylviidae

107. Lesser Whitethroat (*Curruca curruca*) is a species which has been recorded only twice in our wetland on November of 2016 and 2018 when a single bird was seen. Its status is Uncertain (U).

Passeriformes: Leiothrichidae

108. Yellow-billed Babbler (*Argya affinis*) is a Resident (R) species with gregarious nature that has been regularly recorded in our lake. The highest counts were 33 and 30 in August 2016 and June 2019 respectively.

Passeriformes: Sturnidae

109. Rosy Starling	<p>Rosy Starling</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
110. Chestnut-tailed Starling	<p>Chestnut-tailed Starling</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
111. Common Myna	<p>Common Myna</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
112. Jungle Myna	<p>Jungle Myna</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

109. Rosy Starling (*Pastor roseus*) is an irruptive species that has been recorded only thrice, all of them in winter and whose counts are 250, 30 and 41 in February 2015, March 2015, and March 2017 respectively. Its status is Uncertain (U).

110. Chestnut-tailed Starling (*Sturnia malabarica*) is an extremely uncommon species that has been recorded only once when three were sighted in February 2016 and therefore classified as Uncertain (U).

111. Common Myna (*Acridotheres tristis*) is a Resident (R) species that has been one of the most reliable abundant species other than House Crow (#95) sighted in our lake. Its highest count was 150 in March 2015 and there are numerous counts which have exceeded 50. It is worth mentioning that these counts are the best possible estimates given its mobility and abundance.

Fig. 28: Mean population with error bars of the Common Myna

112. Jungle Myna (*Acridotheres fuscus*) is a Resident (R) species which is infrequently sighted in our lake. The highest count was in January 2019 when 17 of them were recorded.

Passeriformes: Muscicapidae

113. Oriental Magpie Robin (*Copsychus saularis*) is a species with a single sighting in May 2016 and thus Uncertain (U).

114. Pied Bushchat (*Saxicola caprata*) is a Resident (R) species which has been fairly frequently sighted during our counts with a high count of three birds on multiple occasions.

Passeriformes: Dicaeidae

115. Pale-billed Flowerpecker (*Dicaeum erythrorhynchos*) is a Resident (R) species that has been recorded consistently during our counts. The highest counts were seven and six sighted in July 2015 and January 2016 respectively.

Passeriformes: Nectariniidae

116. Purple-rumped Sunbird (*Leptocoma zeylonica*) is a Resident (R) species that has been sighted regularly in our counts. The highest counts were recorded in April 2015 and January 2017 when ten and 12 birds were sighted respectively.

117. Purple Sunbird (*Cinnyris asiaticus*) is a Resident (R) species with inconsistent sightings and the highest count were three and two in March 2016 and May 2016 respectively.

118. Loten's Sunbird (*Cinnyris lotenius*) is a Resident (R) species which has been sighted sporadically during our counts. The highest count was three recorded in August 2014.

Passeriformes: Ploceidae

119. Baya Weaver (*Ploceus philippinus*) is a species that was sighted only twice in our lake and therefore Uncertain (U). The counts were 20 and two in May 2017 and December 2019 respectively.

Passeriformes: Estrildidae

120. Scaly-breasted Munia (*Lonchura punctulata*) is a species that has been recorded only twice, four in August 2015 and three in September 2016. Its status is Uncertain (U).

Passeriformes: Passeridae

121. House Sparrow (*Passer domesticus*) is a species which has only two records in this lake, three in July 2014 and one in August 2016 and thus Uncertain (U).

Passeriformes: Motacillidae

Box 7:

Wagtails as a group prefer moist mudflats in wetlands and are generally sighted in water levels between medium and low when such conditions are prevalent.

122. Western Yellow Wagtail	<p>Western Yellow Wagtail</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
123. White-browed Wagtail	<p>White-browed Wagtail</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
124. White Wagtail	<p>White Wagtail</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>
125. Paddyfield Pipit	<p>Paddyfield Pipit</p> <p>January February March April May June July August September October November December</p>

122. Western Yellow Wagtail (*Motacilla flava*) is a Winter Migrant (WM) species in our region and its incidence peaks during the northward migratory months starting from February onwards. The highest counts were 65, 101, 43 in March 2015, February 2017 and February 2018 respectively.

123. White-browed Wagtail (*Motacilla maderaspatensis*) is a Resident (R) species that has been recorded reliably in our lake. This species of Wagtail even though present in wetlands is not exclusively tied to such a habitat. The presence of any amount of moisture being the only

basic requirement, this species is sighted in surrounding areas in a widespread manner. The highest counts were ten and seven in July 2015 and July 2016 respectively.

124. White Wagtail (*Motacilla alba*) is a species which is Uncertain (U) in our lake and a single bird has been recorded on four different occasions.

125. Paddyfield Pipit (*Anthus rufulus*) is a Resident (R) species that is often sighted as the water level decreases usually from February onwards until the monsoon arrives. The highest was four recorded in June 2014 when the lake was dry.

Additional Graphs:

Fig. 29: The average occurrence of waterbirds based on water level

Fig. 30: A scatter plot of average count of waterbirds with their corresponding water levels

Discussion and Conclusion:

It is worth repeating that our study emphasizes the importance of monitoring common birds. According to Gregory et al. 2003, Gregory & Van Strien 2010,

- Even a small decline in the abundance of common species could result in large absolute loss of both individuals and biomass, that might seriously disrupt the ecosystem's structure, function, and services.
- The common birds are reliable "Quality of Life" indicators and the loss of such a critical anchor might be irreversible in the long run.

India currently is home to 17.8% of the world population living in an area of only 2.42% of the Earth's surface (Foote et al., 1996). Therefore, even a small loss of wetland area has a larger impact in the country.

The devastating flash floods in major cities of India like Mumbai, Chennai, Hyderabad, and New Delhi especially experienced from 2010 onwards have been well documented in newspaper reports such as "Time for a 'sponge cities' mission in India" by Kabeer Arora and "How Lake encroachments and official inaction led to floods in Hyderabad" by Swathi Vadlamudi, both published in The Hindu. The principal reason attributed to the tragic occurrence of these flash floods is the gradual and steady decline in wetlands over the long term as a result of uncontrolled building and poor urban planning.

Table 2: Birds of Perur Lake, Coimbatore

Sl.No	Common name	Scientific name	Status	Population trend in Perur Lake (Average)	Distribution
ANSERIFORMES: Anatidae					
1	Lesser Whistling Duck*	<i>Dendrocygna javanica</i>	R / LM	Declining	Uncommon
2	Cotton Pygmy-goose	<i>Nettapus coromandelianus</i>	LM	Unrecorded since Dec-2015	Rare
3	Garganey*	<i>Spatula querquedula</i>	WM	Declining	Fairly Common
4	Northern Shoveler	<i>Spatula clypeata</i>	WM	Declining	Uncommon
5	Northern Pintail	<i>Anas acuta</i>	WM	Declining	Uncommon
6	Common Teal	<i>Anas crecca</i>	U	Declining	Rare
7	Indian Spot-billed Duck*	<i>Anas poecilorhyncha</i>	R	Declining	Common
GALLIFORMES: Phasianidae					
8	Indian Peafowl	<i>Pavo cristatus</i>	R	Consistent	Uncommon
9	Grey Francolin	<i>Francolinus pondicerianus</i>	R	Consistent	Uncommon
PODICIPEDIFORMES: Podicipedidae					
10	Little Grebe*	<i>Tachybaptus ruficollis</i>	R	Declining	Uncommon
COLUMBIFORMES: Columbidae					
11	Rock Pigeon	<i>Columba livia</i>	R	Consistent	Common
12	Eurasian Collared Dove	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
13	Spotted Dove	<i>Streptopelia chinensis</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
14	Laughing Dove	<i>Streptopelia senegalensis</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
CUCULIFORMES: Cuculidae					
15	Greater Coucal	<i>Centropus sinensis</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
16	Blue-faced Malkoha	<i>Phaenicophaeus viridirostris</i>	U	Sighted only once in Feb-2020	Rare
17	Pied Cuckoo	<i>Clamator jacobinus</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
18	Asian Koel	<i>Eudynamis scolopaceus</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
19	Grey-bellied Cuckoo	<i>Cacomantis passerinus</i>	U	Sighted only once in Mar-2018	Rare
20	Common Hawk Cuckoo	<i>Hierococcyx varius</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
CAPRIMULGIFORMES: Apodidae					
21	Brown-backed Needletail	<i>Hirundapus giganteus</i>	U	Irruptive	Rare
22	Indian Swiftlet	<i>Aerodramus unicolor</i>	U	Irruptive	Rare
23	Alpine Swift	<i>Tachymarptis melba</i>	U	Irruptive	Rare
24	Indian House Swift	<i>Apus affinis</i>	U	Irruptive	Rare
25	Asian Palm Swift	<i>Cypsiurus balasiensis</i>	R	Declining	Abundant
GRUIFORMES: Rallidae					
26	Common Moorhen	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	R	Declining	Uncommon
27	Eurasian Coot*	<i>Fulica atra</i>	R	Declining	Common
28	Grey-headed Swamphen	<i>Porphyrio poliocephalus</i>	R	Declining	Fairly Common
29	White-breasted Waterhen	<i>Amaurornis phoenicurus</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
CHARADRIIFORMES: Recurvirostridae					
30	Black-winged Stilt*	<i>Himantopus himantopus</i>	LM	Declining. Juvenile chick recorded in Jul-2019	Uncommon

	CHARADRIIFORMES: Charadriidae				
31	Red-wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
32	Kentish Plover	<i>Charadrius alexandrinus</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
33	Little Ringed Plover*	<i>Charadrius dubius</i>	R/WM	Declining	Fairly Common
	CHARADRIIFORMES: Jacanidae				
34	Pheasant-tailed Jacana	<i>Hydrophasianus chirurgus</i>	U	Erratic. Last sighted in Jan-2015	Rare
35	Bronze-winged Jacana	<i>Metopidius indicus</i>	U	Erratic. Last sighted in Aug-2015	Rare
	CHARADRIIFORMES: Scolopacidae				
36	Temminck's Stint	<i>Calidris temminckii</i>	WM	Consistent	Uncommon
37	Little Stint	<i>Calidris minuta</i>	WM	Declining	Uncommon
38	Common Sandpiper*	<i>Actitis hypoleucos</i>	WM	Declining	Fairly Common
39	Green Sandpiper	<i>Tringa ochropus</i>	WM	Declining	Uncommon
40	Common Greenshank	<i>Tringa nebularia</i>	WM	Consistent	Uncommon
41	Marsh Sandpiper	<i>Tringa stagnatilis</i>	WM	Consistent	Rare
42	Wood Sandpiper*	<i>Tringa glareola</i>	WM	Declining	Fairly Common
	CHARADRIIFORMES: Laridae				
43	Whiskered Tern	<i>Chlidonias hybrida</i>	WM	Irruptive based on water level	Uncommon
44	River Tern	<i>Sterna aurantia</i>	WM	Erratic	Rare
	CICONIIFORMES: Ciconiidae				
45	Asian Openbill*	<i>Anastomus oscitans</i>	LM	Declining	Common
46	Woolly-necked Stork	<i>Ciconia episcopus</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
47	Painted Stork	<i>Mycteria leucocephala</i>	LM	Consistent	Fairly Common
	SULIFORMES: Anhingidae				
48	Oriental Darter	<i>Anhinga melanogaster</i>	R	Apparent Increase. Nesting recorded	Fairly Common
	SULIFORMES: Phalacrocoracidae				
49	Little Cormorant	<i>Microcarbo niger</i>	R	Apparent Increase	Abundant
50	Indian Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax fuscicollis</i>	R	Apparent Increase	Fairly Common
51	Great Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>	LM	Erratic	Rare
	PELECANIFORMES: Pelecanidae				
52	Spot-billed Pelican	<i>Pelecanus philippensis</i>	LM	Declining	Uncommon
	PELECANIFORMES: Ardeidae				
53	Yellow Bittern	<i>Ixobrychus sinensis</i>	U	Erratic. Last sighted in Mar-2016	Rare
54	Cinnamon Bittern	<i>Ixobrychus cinnamomeus</i>	U	Erratic. Last sighted in Apr-2016	Rare
55	Grey Heron	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
56	Purple Heron	<i>Ardea purpurea</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
57	Great Egret	<i>Ardea alba</i>	LM	Declining	Fairly Common
58	Intermediate Egret	<i>Ardea intermedia</i>	LM	Declining	Fairly Common
59	Little Egret*	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	LM	Declining	Common
60	Cattle Egret	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	LM	Consistent	Fairly Common
61	Indian Pond Heron*	<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	R	Declining	Common
62	Striated Heron	<i>Butorides striata</i>	U	Erratic	Rare

63	Black-crowned Night Heron	<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>	R	Consistent	Uncommon
PELECANIFORMES: Threskiornithidae					
64	Glossy Ibis	<i>Plegadis falcinellus</i>	WM	Declining	Uncommon
65	Black-headed Ibis	<i>Threskiornis melanocephalus</i>	LM	Erratic	Uncommon
66	Eurasian Spoonbill	<i>Platalea leucorodia</i>	LM	Erratic	Uncommon
ACCIPITRIFORMES: Accipitridae					
67	Oriental Honey Buzzard	<i>Pernis ptilorhynchus</i>	R	Erratic	Rare
68	Black Eagle	<i>Ictinaetus malaiensis</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
69	Booted Eagle	<i>Hieraaetus pennatus</i>	U	Declining	Rare
70	Western Marsh Harrier	<i>Circus aeruginosus</i>	U	Last sighted in Feb-2016	Rare
71	Shikra	<i>Accipiter badius</i>	R	Consistent	Rare
72	Black Kite	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	R	Consistent	Uncommon
73	Brahminy Kite	<i>Haliastur indus</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
STRIGIFORMES: Strigidae					
74	Spotted Owlet	<i>Athene brama</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
BUCEROTIFORMES: Upupidae					
75	Common Hoopoe	<i>Upupa epops</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
BUCEROTIFORMES: Bucerotidae					
76	Indian Grey Hornbill	<i>Ocyrceros birostris</i>	U	Sighted only once in Oct-2014	Rare
CORACIIFORMES: Alcedinidae					
77	Common Kingfisher	<i>Alcedo atthis</i>	R	Consistent	Uncommon
78	Stork-billed Kingfisher	<i>Pelargopsis capensis</i>	U	Sighted only once in Feb-2019	Rare
79	White-throated Kingfisher	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
80	Pied Kingfisher	<i>Ceryle rudis</i>	R	Last sighted in Jul-2016	Rare
CORACIIFORMES: Meropidae					
81	Green Bee-eater	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
82	Blue-tailed Bee-eater	<i>Merops philippinus</i>	WM	Declining	Fairly Common
CORACIIFORMES: Coraciidae					
83	Indian Roller	<i>Coracias benghalensis</i>	R	Erratic	Uncommon
PICIFORMES: Megalaimidae					
84	Coppersmith Barbet	<i>Psilopogon haemacephalus</i>	R	Erratic	Rare
PICIFORMES: Picidae					
85	Black-rumped Flameback	<i>Dinopium benghalense</i>	R	Consistent	Uncommon
FALCONIFORMES: Falconidae					
86	Peregrine Falcon	<i>Falco peregrinus</i>	U	Last sighted in Apr-2018	Rare
PSITTACIFORMES: Psittaculidae					
87	Rose-ringed Parakeet	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
PASSERIFORMES: Oriolidae					
88	Eurasian Golden Oriole	<i>Oriolus oriolus</i>	WM	Erratic	Rare
PASSERIFORMES: Artamidae					
89	Ashy Woodswallow	<i>Artamus fuscus</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
PASSERIFORMES: Aegithinidae					
90	Common Iora	<i>Aegithina tiphia</i>	U	Erratic	Rare

	PASSERIFORMES: Dicruridae				
91	Black Drongo	<i>Dicrurus macrocercus</i>	R	Consistent	Uncommon
	PASSERIFORMES: Monarchidae				
92	Indian Paradise-flycatcher	<i>Terpsiphone paradisi</i>	U	Sighted only once in Nov-2018	Rare
	PASSERIFORMES: Laniidae				
93	Brown Shrike	<i>Lanius cristatus</i>	WM	Declining	Uncommon
	PASSERIFORMES: Corvidae				
94	Rufous Treepie	<i>Dendrocitta vagabunda</i>	R	Consistent	Uncommon
95	House Crow	<i>Corvus splendens</i>	R	Consistent	Abundant
96	Large-billed Crow	<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
	PASSERIFORMES: Cisticolidae				
97	Common Tailorbird	<i>Orthotomus sutorius</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
98	Ashy Prinia	<i>Prinia socialis</i>	R	Declining	Fairly Common
	PASSERIFORMES: Acrocephalidae				
99	Booted Warbler	<i>Iduna caligata</i>	WM	Declining	Uncommon
100	Sykes's Warbler	<i>Iduna rama</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
101	Blyth's Reed Warbler	<i>Acrocephalus dumetorum</i>	WM	Declining	Uncommon
102	Clamorous Reed Warbler	<i>Acrocephalus stentoreus</i>	LM	Erratic	Rare
	PASSERIFORMES: Hirundinidae				
103	Barn Swallow	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	WM	Declining	Common
104	Red-rumped Swallow	<i>Cecropis daurica</i>	LM	Consistent	Uncommon
105	Northern House Martin	<i>Delichon urbicum</i>	U	Sighted only once in Feb-2016	Rare
	PASSERIFORMES: Pycnonotidae				
106	Red-vented Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	R	Consistent	Uncommon
	PASSERIFORMES: Sylviidae				
107	Lesser Whitethroat	<i>Curruca curruca</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
	PASSERIFORMES: Leiothrichidae				
108	Yellow-billed Babbler	<i>Argya affinis</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
	PASSERIFORMES: Sturnidae				
109	Rosy Starling	<i>Pastor roseus</i>	U	Irruptive	Rare
110	Chestnut-tailed Starling	<i>Sturnia malabarica</i>	U	Sighted only once in Feb-2016	Rare
111	Common Myna	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	R	Consistent	Common
112	Jungle Myna	<i>Acridotheres fuscus</i>	R	Erratic	Rare
	PASSERIFORMES: Muscicapidae				
113	Oriental Magpie Robin	<i>Copsychus saularis</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
114	Pied Bushchat	<i>Saxicola caprata</i>	R	Declining	Uncommon
	PASSERIFORMES: Dicaeidae				
115	Pale-billed Flowerpecker	<i>Dicaeum erythrorhynchos</i>	R	Consistent	Uncommon
	PASSERIFORMES: Nectariniidae				
116	Purple-rumped Sunbird	<i>Leptocoma zeylonica</i>	R	Consistent	Fairly Common
117	Purple Sunbird	<i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i>	R	Consistent	Rare
118	Loten's Sunbird	<i>Cinnyris lotenius</i>	R	Erratic	Rare

	PASSERIFORMES: Ploceidae				
119	Baya Weaver	<i>Ploceus philippinus</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
	PASSERIFORMES: Estrildidae				
120	Scaly-breasted Munia	<i>Lonchura punctulata</i>	U	Erratic	Rare
	PASSERIFORMES: Passeridae				
121	House Sparrow	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	U	Last sighted in Aug-2016	Rare
	PASSERIFORMES: Motacillidae				
122	Western Yellow Wagtail	<i>Motacilla flava</i>	WM	Declining	Uncommon
123	White-browed Wagtail	<i>Motacilla maderaspatensis</i>	R	Consistent	Uncommon
124	White Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	U	Erratic. Last sighted in Feb-2018	Rare
125	Paddyfield Pipit	<i>Anthus rufulus</i>	R	Declining. Last sighted in Jun-2018	Rare

* Species with asterisk mark and highlighted in red are discussed in Table 8 of the main manuscript.

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